

Structural and Electrical Properties of $YXFeSbO_7$ (X=lanthanons or bismuth) Pyrochlores

S. L. PATIL and V. S. DARSHANE

Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Institute of Science, Bombay-400 082

Manuscript received 19 March 1981, accepted 31 August 1981

X-ray investigation of $YXFeSbO_7$ (where X=lanthanons or bismuth) compounds is carried out to find out limits of pyrochlore formation. Except $YLaFeSbO_7$, all the compounds show pyrochlore structure. On the basis of radius ratio, stability of the compounds extends from 1.60 to 1.71 and distorted structure is observed when it is 1.74. A linear plot is observed when lattice parameters of the compounds are plotted against Shannon and Prewitt's ionic radii of X^{3+} ions. The electrical resistivity temperature behaviour obeys the relation $\rho = \rho_0 \exp \frac{\Delta E}{kT}$, exhibiting semiconducting nature of the compounds. The dielectric constant measurements show no variation when measured up to 773K.

ANALYSIS of natural pyrochlore minerals¹ suggests that wide variety of both cationic and anionic substitutions are possible. Literature survey, however, revealed that very little work is reported on pyrochlores where substitution of cation is carried out at A as well as at B sites²⁻⁶. Pyrochlore compounds possess interesting electrical properties⁷. Mixed pyrochlores of the type $YXFeSbO_7$ (X=lanthanons or bismuth) have been synthesised and investigated by X-ray diffraction technique. The results are reported here.

Pyrochlore structure has the general formula $A_2B_2O_7$. It has corner shared octahedra containing a small B cation in octahedral coordination with a relatively large A cation in the interstices of the frame-work of the octahedra. The stability of the structure arises mainly from the electrostatic energy and hence the relative size of the A and B cations are important. The necessity for octahedral coordination sets a lower limit of 0.60 Å as the size of the B cation in oxidic systems, since an ion smaller than this does not achieve optimum B-O separation and stabilizes a structure with lower coordination. This minimum size of the B ion sets a lower bound on the size of the A cation of 0.9 Å. That is why the large lanthanons preferentially occupy the A site in the $A_2B_2O_7$ structure. The space group for pyrochlore compounds is $Fd\bar{3}m - O_h^v$.

Materials and Methods: The compounds mentioned in Table 1 were prepared by using standard ceramic technique. Initially, the compound $FeSbO_4$ was prepared by heating ferric oxide and antimony trioxide in molar proportion in air. The compound $FeSbO_4$ is tetragonal with $a=4.64$ and $c=3.08$ Å. This value agrees with the value reported by Stewart *et al*⁸. The compounds $YXFeSbO_7$ (X=lanthanons or bismuth) were prepared by mixing Y_2O_3 , Ln_2O_3 and $FeSbO_4$ in molar proportion. The pellets were prepared by compressing

the powder to 20,000 p.s.i. using polyvinyl acetate as a binder. The pellets were first heated at 900° for 60 hrs and then at 1350° for 40 hrs. X-ray diffraction patterns were taken on Philips machine using Cu K α radiation with Ni filter. The dc resistivity and dielectric constant measurements were carried on LCR Marconi bridge using two probe technique.

Results and Discussion

The results of X-ray analysis are given in Table 1 and crystallographic data of the compound $YDyFeSbO_7$ in Table 2. It is observed that except $YLaFeSbO_7$ all the compounds exhibit pyrochlore

TABLE 1

Compound	Radius ratio $\frac{A^{3+}X^{3+}}{B^{3+}B^{3+}}$	Lattice parameter A	Resistivity at 423K (ohm-cm)	Dielectric constant at 1KHz (300K)	Activation energy (eV)
$YLaFeSbO_7$	1.74	Distorted pyrochlore	3.0×10^9	154	0.75
$YPrFeSbO_7$	1.71	10.80	6.7×10^{10}	162	0.86
$YNdFeSbO_7$	1.69	10.29	1.3×10^{10}	179	0.84
$YBiFeSbO_7$	1.69	10.29	1.1×10^{10}	157	0.90
$YSmFeSbO_7$	1.67	10.27	2.7×10^{10}	144	0.90
$YGdFeSbO_7$	1.65	10.24	1.7×10^9	107	0.97
$YDyFeSbO_7$	1.62	10.22	6.9×10^9	121	0.95
$YErFeSbO_7$	1.60	10.19	1.9×10^{10}	156	1.08

TABLE 2—INDEXED X-RAY DIFFRACTION PATTERN OF $YDyFeSbO_7$

I/I ₀	d _(obs)	d _(cal)	hkl
100	2.952	2.952	222
40	2.554	2.555	400
6	2.345	2.347	331
48	1.808	1.807	440
39	1.542	1.542	622
9	1.476	1.475	444

Structural type—Pyrochlore
Lattice constant—10.22Å.

structure. It seems that due to large size of La^{3+} (1.18 Å), it cannot be safely accommodated at A site of pyrochlore lattice. YLaFeSbO_7 , therefore, shows distorted pyrochlore structure. When the stability of the compounds mentioned in Table 1 is considered on the basis of radius ratio $(A^{3+}X^{3+})/(B^{3+}B^{3+})$, it is observed that the stability limit extends from 1.60 to 1.71. A distorted structure is observed when it is 1.74 (YLaFeSbO_7). Radius ratios are calculated by using Shannon and Prewitt's ionic radii⁹. A plot of lattice parameter against ionic radius of X^{3+} ion shows linear relationship (Fig. 1). Deviation from linearity in case of YBiFeSbO_7 may be due to the difference in electronegativity between lanthanons and bismuth. We also observed similar behaviour in PbXTiNbO_7 (X=lanthanons or bismuth) as reported earlier⁶. Knop *et al*⁸ reported YBiTi_2O_7 and $\text{Bi}_2\text{Ti}_2\text{O}_7$ not to possess pyrochlore structure. We have, however, observed that $\text{Y}_{1-x}\text{Bi}_x\text{FeSbO}_7$ has pyrochlore structure.

Fig. 1. Lattice parameter vs ionic radius of X^{3+} ion.

The dc resistivity of the compounds, when measured as a function of temperature, varies between 10^{10} and 10^6 ohm-cm. The plot of $\log \rho$ vs $1/T$ was linear indicating semiconducting nature (Fig. 2). The compounds show fairly high activation energies which vary between 0.75 and 1.03 eV. From Fig. 3 it is observed that there is a decreasing trend in activation energy as the size of lanthanide ion increases in the series YXFeSbO_7 . Similar trend has also been observed by Bouchard and Gillson¹⁰ and Subba Rao *et al*¹¹ ($\text{Ln}_2\text{MO}_3\text{O}_7$ pyrochlore). Fairly high resistivity of compounds indicates the presence of iron in Fe^{3+} state only. Fe_3O_4 which belongs to spinel type has ionic configuration $\text{Fe}^{3+}[\text{Fe}^{2+}\text{Fe}^{3+}]\text{O}_4$. This compound possesses low resistivity ($\sim 10^{-2}$ ohm-cm) due to the presence of iron at the B site in two different oxidation states¹². High resistivity of YXFeSbO_7 pyrochlores also suggests that d electrons must be

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log \rho$ vs $10^3/T$ for compounds YXFeSbO_7 , where A- YErFeSbO_7 , B- YGdFeSbO_7 , C- YNdFeSbO_7 , D- YLaFeSbO_7 , E- YBiFeSbO_7 , F- YSmFeSbO_7 , G- YPrFeSbO_7 .

Fig. 3. Plot of activation energy vs ionic radius of X^{3+} ion for the compounds YXFeSbO_7 , where X=lanthanide or bismuth ion.

present in localised state and electrical conduction takes place through A-O interaction due to thermal excitation. The Mössbauer spectroscopic investigation of these compounds is in progress.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to U. G. C., New Delhi for a research grant.

References

1. D. D. HOGARTH, *Can. Min.*, 1959, **6**, 610.
2. I. N. BELYAEV, E. G. FESSENKO, A. F. PEPSUNK'KO and YA. CHERNER, *E. Izv. Akad. Nauk. SSSR, Ser. Fiz.*, 1975, **39**, 1103.
3. O. KNOP, F. BRISSE and L. CASTELLIZ, *Cand. J. Chem.*, 1969, **47**, 971.
4. E. ALRESHIN and R. ROY, *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, 1962, **45**, 18.
5. V. S. DARSHANE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 108.
6. S. L. PATIL and V. S. DARSHANE, *Curr. Sci.*, 1980, **49**, 430.
7. C. N. R. RAO and G. V. SUBBA RAO, *Phys. Stat. Solids*, 1970, **A1**, 597.
8. D. J. STEWART, O. KNOP, C. AYASSE and F. W. D. WOODHAMS, *Cand. J. Chem.*, 1972, **50**, 690.
9. R. D. SHANNON and C. T. PREWITT, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1970, **B26**, 1076.
10. R. J. BOUCHARD and S. L. GILLSON, *Mat. Res. Bull.*, 1971, **6**, 669.
11. M. A. SUBRAMANIAN, G. ARAVAMADAN and G. V. SUBBA RAO, *Nuclear Phys. and Solid State Phys. Sym.* (DAE, India), 1979, **22c**, 301.
12. E. J. W. VERWEY, *Nature*, 1939, **144**, 327.